

Practice Abstract no. 44

Data sovereignty and trust

Driven by a continuous process of research, dialogue, and reflection, and ultimately validated with the support of the FOODITY Innovators, a series of recommendations are proposed as a roadmap for building responsible, inclusive, and user-driven digital food systems, ensuring that data works for people, not the other way around.

Recommendations for data sovereignty and trust

Ensuring data sovereignty and trust is key to empowering users in the digital space. These recommendations highlight practical ways to give people real control over their data, strengthen transparency, and create systems that balance privacy with meaningful participation.

1. **Enable Control Over Personal Data:** Allow users to view, edit, delete, and transfer their data. Co-create intuitive control features with users and provide tutorials (Hummel et al., 2021).
2. **Ensure Transparency and Informed Consent:** Replace legal jargon with clear explanations of data use. Make consent processes easy to understand and reverse (HLPE, 2022).
3. **Support Reversibility and Data Portability:** Enable users to withdraw permissions and export their data without barriers. Design systems that prevent vendor lock-in (Hummel et al., 2021).
4. **Protect Against Data Misuse with Strong Safeguards:** Use encryption, anonymisation, and robust security policies to protect sensitive data (Gendron & Killian, 2020).
5. **Raise Awareness of Data Rights and Responsibilities:** Include awareness-building elements during development and in-app experiences to empower users to exercise their data rights (HLPE, 2022).
6. **Enable Participation in Data Governance:** Involve users in co-creating governance models and terms of service, ensuring their values are reflected in data practices (Hummel et al., 2021).
7. **Balance Data Sharing and Privacy with Clear Options:** Offer customisable privacy settings and only collect what is strictly necessary. Communicate clearly how data will be used (Gendron & Killian, 2020).
8. **Foster Trust Through Respectful Engagement:** Build trust through transparency, ongoing communication, and collaborations with trusted intermediaries like doctors ((HLPE, 2022).
9. **Anchor Development in Legal and Ethical Frameworks:** Ensure compliance with regulations like GDPR and make legal rights accessible and actionable for users (Hummel et al., 2021).

10. **Design for Digital Sovereignty Across All User Groups:** Develop inclusive interfaces that support autonomy across diverse populations, including older adults and people with low digital literacy (Kitkowska et al., 2023).

References:

- Gendron, J., & Killian, D. (2020). Data citizens: Rights and responsibilities in a data republic. Data Democracy, Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-818366-3.00002-2>
- HLPE. (2022). Data collection and analysis tools for food security and nutrition (Report No. 17).
- Hummel, P., Braun, M., Augsberg, S., Ulmenstein, U. von, & Dabrock, P. (2021). Datensouveränität als informationelle Freiheitsgestaltung. In P. Hummel, M. Braun, S. Augsberg, U. von Ulmenstein, & P. Dabrock, Datensouveränität (S. 1–12). Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-33755-1_1
- Kitkowska, A., Shulman, Y., Martucci, L. A., & Wästlund, E. (2023). Designing for privacy: Exploring the influence of affect and individual characteristics on users' interactions with privacy policies. Computers & Security, 134, 103468. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cose.2023.103468>
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The aforementioned information is available and further detailed in the report "Recommendations for data sovereignty of consumers, engagement processes in development phase, tools for data based systems and data sharing processes." (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17360930>)

